

ADVANCES IN THE UNDERSTANDING OF INELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF ORDERED INTERMETALLICS

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ABSTRACT

The limited ductility which ordered intermetallics exhibit, is discussed on the basis of new theoretical developments in understanding their inelastic behavior. These developments address the mechanisms of dislocation for limited slip, cross slip, twinning, phase transition, thermo-mechanical effects. The evolution mechanism at the crystal level is then incorporated in continuum plasticity theory. The continuum approach involves phenomenological, micro-mechanical, statistically based plasticity theories, and the prediction of fracture behavior of ordered intermetallics. These theories are cast in an incremental form for incorporation in computational codes. Finally, new developments on the understanding of fracture of ordered intermetallics based on atomistic-to-continuum mechanical behavior and the competition between ductile slip and brittle separation are used in developing new fracture criteria.

INTRODUCTION

Ordered intermetallic composites have mechanical and physical attributes that are attractive for several advanced materials applications. In addition to strength and low density advantages, intermetallics are in general inherently more resistant to oxidation. Unfortunately, many intermetallics such as titanium aluminides, nickel aluminides, and others that are of interest in corrosive environment, are brittle and lack appreciable ductility (less than one percent).

Research directed towards a comprehensive understanding of the factors controlling the strength and fracture of very high melting point ordered intermetallic alloys will permit development of new superior materials for structural applications. In order to address these issues, the efforts of both applied mechanics and material science research have been incorporated in a multi-disciplinary project involving new plasticity and fracture mechanics formulations, mechanical property measurement, electronic structure calculations, new alloy ordered intermetallics modification, and synthesis and processing. This paper will concentrate on the continuum mechanics aspects of this research.

Advances in the development of crystal plasticity theory for ordered intermetallics promises to lead to the engineering of new intermetallic composites and fiber/matrix interfaces, by exploiting their limited ductility. These recent theories incorporate the limited plasticity due to limited number of slip planes, non-Schmid effects and anomalies in thermo-mechanical behavior. The approach used in these developments is to address the various mechanisms of dislocation limited slip, cross slip, twinning, phase transition, evolution mechanisms at the crystal level, which can then be incorporated in a continuum plasticity theory. The continuum approach involves phenomenological, micro-mechanical, and statistically based plasticity theories, and the prediction of fracture behavior of ordered intermetallics. The incremental form of these theories is then incorporated in finite element computational codes for the engineering of intermetallic composites. Finally, a new area of research in the understanding of fracture of ordered intermetallics is addressing atomistic-to-continuum mechanical behavior. As a result of which, the competition between ductile slip at crack tips and Griffith surface energy of separation is used for developing new fracture criteria.

1. CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONS AND MODELING OF DUCTILE BEHAVIOR:

In order to analyze ordered intermetallic alloy components or structures using current finite element capabilities, dislocation mechanics in the framework of classical plasticity theories were developed. Because of the crystallographic nature of slip in single crystals, plastic flow is confined to narrow regions across which displacements and stresses vary rapidly. Because the geometry of the slip patterns is not known a priori, computer modeling is far more complicated than that of materials which obey classical plasticity formulations.

1.1. DISLOCATION MECHANICS IN THE FRAMEWORK CLASSICAL PLASTICITY THEORY:

Based on the well accepted notion of a crystal at the lattice scale and with particular reference to inelastic behavior of ordered intermetallics, a macroscopic dynamical theory of structured solid is constructed by Naghdi [1]. This theory incorporates a wide variety of microstructural processes occurring at various physical scales and has a range approaching the atomic scale. These processes include the effect of point defects, as well as the notion of individual dislocations, which are modelled as continuous dislocations at the macroscopic scale.

It is obvious that such theory would have to deal with very large strains, rotations and very high rates at the micro level even though on the macro scale such effects might be small. The basic theory [1] employs the so called Cosserat continuum concept, or directors which represents the motion of the lattice, and determines the additional momentum-like balance laws for the rate of change of lattice director triad. A unique measure of plastic deformation is therefore defined to differentiate between reversible and irreversible processes at the crystal level. This basic development provides the structure of the constitutive response functions for both large deformation visco-plasticity and rate independent plasticity. The theory was applied to plain strain deformation of a single crystal with two slip planes and a sinusoidal form of dislocation distribution and were carried out up to strains of 27.5%. The resulting engineering stress/strain behavior indicates large localized ductile behavior. After general yield is achieved the material softens, then hardens again at large strains.

1.2. STATISTICAL MECHANICS APPROACH TO CONSTITUTIVE MODELING OF ORDERED INTERMETALLICS:

Ordered intermetallics have several thermomechanical anomalies which represent major difficulties in constitutive modeling. For example in Ni_3Al , for sufficiently large offset strain, the conventional yield stress in uniaxial tension increases with temperature up to a peak and subsequently decreases at a temperature of 600° F. This behavior is a function of the offset strain adopted by the experimentalist. Similar anomaly exists for the hardening rate which has two peaks at intermediate temperature (400° F to 600° F). Another complication exists by an anomaly related to the asymmetry in tension and compression behavior. Several material scientists attributed such anomalies to "non-Schmid" effects. Modeling such behavior in multi-axial stress states, and using current plasticity theories, for finite strains, finite rotations, and high rates is extremely complex and may lead to incorrect predictions.

Cuintino and Ortiz [2] used a statistical mechanics approach in order to develop constitutive relations based on forest dislocation hardening. The model accounts for forest hardening, dislocation slip on octahedral system, forest obstacles, cross-slip pinning mechanism, rate of obstacle generation, super-partial dislocation and other "non Schmid" effects. The model is capable to simulating short range interactions between pairs of dislocations and the kinetics of dislocation multiplication. Accounting for all these mechanisms seems formidable, however the statistical mechanics approach allows the description of each mechanism as a simple physical phenomena, amenable to rigorous analytical treatment within the framework of non-equilibrium statistical mechanics. Because of the Markovian nature of the dislocation flights, the evolution equations are well known, and can be integrated; they lead to the proper cumulative behavior of the continuum. Using this approach Cuintino and Ortiz [2] cast it in a general finite strain form, and were able to explain the yield vs. temperature and hardening anomalies in L1_2 intermetallic based on the forest dislocation and on the true elastic limit of the single crystal. They reproduced the stress-strain and hardening of the continuum. In addition they predicted an asymmetry in tension vs. compression, which was also confirmed experimentally.

1.3. LARGE SCALE SIMULATION OF MULTI-CRYSTAL DEFORMATION :

In order to account for non-Schmid effects and localized plastic flow in intermetallic alloys, Dao and Asaro [3] used large scale three dimensional finite-element computations, which can account for all possible dislocation slip mechanisms in polycrystalline ordered intermetallic. This formulation allows for lower symmetry - restricted slip systems, ambient temperature brittleness, and anisotropic crystalline properties. The deviations from Schmid's rule include cross-slip, multi-slip systems in every grain, temperature dependence, rate dependent effects, localized plastic flow and complex temperature dependence. The yield function used also accounts for contributions of all stress components. Among the non-Schmid deviations that this formulation accounts for is phase transition, phenomena observed in intermetallics at high strain rates. If it is ignored in the analysis, lower ductility is realized.

As an example of engineering of materials, this formulation was used in the design of the MMC interface of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ by introducing a intermediate intermetallic CuAl_2 interphase. The interface thus provided a transition from the metallic ductile matrix to the brittle zone. This specific tailored interface MMC $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ was synthesized by Cornie et.al. [11] at MIT,

and gave the predicted properties. Other applications included Ti-Al/Ti₃-Al and NiAl turbine blade design and understanding the failure of cast TiAl intermetallic. Without this specific crystal plasticity theory many of these predictions could not be achieved.

1.4. PHASE TRANSITION IN ORDERED INTERMETALLICS:

Atomistic simulations of crack tips show that stress induced martensitic transformations occur in ordered intermetallics, [10]. These deformations on the atomic level of lattice deformations are referred to as shuffling of the atoms, which is caused by shearing in two directions, before reaching the final crystal structure. These inelastic deformations are exceedingly large, and if exploited properly in the design with ordered intermetallics, could impede their brittle behavior. Although the uniaxial stress-strain curve associated with phase transition could be interpreted as a plastic deformation, such interpretation leads to gross errors in multi-axial stress states. Recently Abeyaratne and Knowles [4] developed a constitutive model based on inelastic behavior, where they introduced additional kinematic relations to relate the conditions for the nucleation of the phase transition. Thermal and inertial effects are included in the analysis.

Escobar and Clifton [6] used the pressure-shear plate impact to study the kinetics of stress phase transitions in intermetallics based on the three-dimensional theoretical treatment of Abeyaratne and Knowles [5]. The deformation of a single crystal Cu-Al-Ni, a shape memory intermetallic alloy, are studied under combined high pressure impact and shear. During the transformation the lattice of the initial phase is separated from the lattice of the final martensitic phase by the so called habit plane. The continuum model for this experiment follows the same axioms discussed above in section 1.1.

2. FRACTURE OF ORDERED INTERMETALLICS

2.2. DE-ADHESION MODEL

Failure within the intermetallics microstructure and especially within the microstructure of composite intermetallics nearly always begins at interfaces. Such interfaces include grain boundaries, particle/matrix interfaces in the composite, and interfaces in layered structures. Understanding these failure mechanisms involves studies of three-dimensional stress plastic strain fields of bimaterial crystalline interfaces. Dao and Asaro [3] performed detailed studies of a particular class of bicrystal with symmetric tilt boundaries. The deformation patterns caused by the crystallographic constraint combined with accurate experiments on bicrystals NiAl are providing an accurate de-adhesion criterion for the failure mechanism.

2.3. COMPETITION BETWEEN BRITTLE AND DUCTILE BEHAVIOR

Advances in material science allow the computation of crystal elastic properties from "ab initio" first principle atomistic simulations. These highly intensive computational simulations are becoming very powerful predictive methods. Such tools have been applied to ordered intermetallic alloys for predicting some of their properties. However there exist a gap in the connection between the atomistic scale and the continuum scale. Recently Rice [7] was able to bridge this gap from the fracture point view and provided an understanding of the competition between brittle vs. ductile response in f.c.c. and b.c.c. metals.

Rice [7] analyzed dislocation nucleation from crack tips using the Peierls' concept. This atomistic concept relates the slip of an atomic lattice to dislocation nucleation. Using the J-integral, an exact solution for the loading at that nucleation instability was obtained. Rice has shown that the energy release rate for the emission of dislocations scales with the energy associated with the sliding of atomic planes past one another. Rice then identified this as a new solid state parameter termed the "Unstable Stacking Energy", which can be used to evaluate dislocation nucleation or ductile crack growth. This energy is the work done in shifting two lattice planes by half the shear needed to nucleate a dislocation, i.e. the (unstable) equilibrium position at which energy of the shearing process is a local maximum. The "Unstable Stacking Energy", being based on the Peierls' concept, can be then estimated using first principle atomistic calculations (methods such as embedded atom method, density function methods and others).

With the results so derived, there is no further need for the introduction of the poorly defined core cut-off at the crack tip in analyzing the dislocation nucleation, introduced by Rice and Thomson model [8].

Brittle response can be calculated using the Griffith cleavage de-cohesion condition governed by the surface energy, while the dislocation nucleation is governed by the unstable stacking energy. Calculations were performed for ordered Ni_3Al . The predictions are compatible with known behavior of the material; it was found that dislocation nucleation vs. cleavage extension, or ductile vs. brittle behavior, is a strong function of the crack direction with respect to the crystal system. These results correspond to a loading for spontaneous nucleation. The theory predicted, for the first time, that the thermal activation will allow nucleation at a finite rate and lower load levels than currently predicted. The results of Rice were recently confirmed by Clapp [10] using an atomistic pair potential method for the case of Nb_3Al and Ni_3Al .

3. FATIGUE OF ORDERED INTERMETALLICS

Lin [9] used the extrusion/intrusion of persistent slip bands model to simulate the high cycle fatigue cracking of ordered intermetallic compounds, where the dislocation Burger's vector is quite long compared to that of disordered alloys. The increased length of the Burger's vector ($[110]$ rather than $1/2[110]$ in f.c.c.) in intermetallics favors planar slip and tends to inhibit multiple slip. This persistent slip band model was applied to ordered and disordered compounds and showed that S-N curve is higher for the ordered alloys. The model showed excellent agreement with experimental S-N results for Ni_3Mn for ordered and disordered compounds from 10^4 up to 10^8 cycles.

4. CONCLUSION

Inelastic deformations of ordered intermetallics provide a means for exploiting their unconventional ductile behavior. Current plasticity theories stand no chance of representing such behavior. It was shown that new plasticity theories based either on classical approaches, or crystal plasticity theories with limited slip, can represent ordered intermetallics accurately. Massive computing, and statistical approaches can then be used to analyze the solid. Advances in continuum - to - atomistic methods for predicting mechanical behavior were shown to offer a means for predicting fracture based on solid state quantities which are calculated from first principles and extended to the continuum.

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